

Photoelectrochemical and corrosion studies on electrodeposited nickel and cobalt containing ZnSe thin films

R. K. Pathak* and Pratibha Sharma

Department of Chemistry, Government P. G. College, Rajgarh-465 661, India

E-mail : pathak02@sancharnet.in

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ZnSe thin films with/without nickel and cobalt incorporation were electrosynthesised by electrochemical co-deposition method. Photoelectrochemical characterization of the electrodeposits of different composition of electroplating solution have been carried out. Current-voltage behaviour of thin films is also taken into consideration for the construction of Tafel plots to determine corrosion rates. Photospectral studies have also been used for the characterization of the electrodeposits.

Photoelectrochemical processes at semiconductor-electrolyte interface have been found for solar energy conversion was suggested by many workers. A large number of studies have been carried out to increase the efficiency and stability of the cell¹⁻⁵. The electrodeposited thin films and electrolyte interface suffer from a major problem of electrochemical corrosion⁶⁻⁸. Thin film synthesized by electrochemical co-deposition are quite attractive from the point of view of photoelectrochemical conversion of solar energy. Electrodeposition has emerged as a simple and cost effective technique for the preparation of thin films. In the present investigation, electrosynthesis of nickel and cobalt containing ZnSe films under different experimental conditions has been done and corrosion rates have been estimated by studying their current-voltage measurements. The photoelectroconvertibility of these preparations depends on the composition of electroplating solution. On the basis of photoaction spectral studies, characterization of the electrodeposits has been attempted.

Results and discussion

Preparation of an electrodeposited semiconductor thin films by electrochemical method requires simultaneous deposition of its constituents inspite of their different deposition potentials. The situation wherein the deposition potential do not differ much, these can be brought to identical values by adjustment of ionic activities of the solution being electrolysed. If the deposition is attempted at a potential beyond the deposition potential of the more electropositive ion, both the ion may discharge together. In order to achieve this objective, polarisation experiments were carried out of an electroplating solution containing 0.1 ZnSO₄ and 0.01 M SeO₂ using platinum electrodes. The current-voltage

Fig. 1. Current-voltage behaviour of ZnSe thin film.

behaviour is shown in Fig.1. This indicates that the possibilities of simultaneous deposition in the potential range from -0.60 to -1.00 V vs SCE. Four electrodes were prepared at different potentials within this range and tested in 1 M ZnSO₄, 0.1 M KI and 0.5 mM I₂ solution for their photoactivity. These exploratory studies show that the electrodeposits obtained at potential of -0.80 V vs SCE yields films with good photoactivity. Accordingly all the preparations were carried out at this potential. In all the case, the electroplating solution contained 0.1 M ZnSO₄, 0.01 M SeO₂ and the trace amount of NiSO₄ and CoSO₄. Summary of experimental data for nickel containing ZnSe is presented in Table 1 and cobalt containing ZnSe is given in Table 2.

During deposition, the current obtained immediately after the application of a step function voltage is known in all cases to decay with time until a steady state current is achieved. This behaviour arises due to formation of semiconductor (SC) layer and generation of depletion layer at the sc-electrolyte interface. The typical plots of variation of current with time during electrodeposition of ZnSe, nickel and cobalt containing ZnSe films at -0.80 V vs SCE is

Table 1. Electrochemical parameters of Ni containing ZnSe thin films

Deposition time = 1 h, deposition potential = -0.800 V vs SCE

Electroplating solution composition			(-) Deposition current (mA cm ⁻²)		Film thickness (10 ⁻⁵ cm)	Photopotential (mV)	Corrosion rate (mpy)
Zn	Se	Ni	Initial	Final			
0.1	0.01	0.0000	0.850	0.050	4.8	160	1.6
0.1	0.01	0.0001	0.910	0.080	5.2	174	0.6
0.1	0.01	0.0002	0.940	0.090	6.4	200	0.5
0.1	0.01	0.0003	0.985	0.120	7.3	190	0.3
0.1	0.01	0.0004	1.000	0.140	8.0	192	0.3

Table 2. Electrochemical parameters of Co containing ZnSe thin films

Deposition time = 1 h, deposition potential = -0.800 V vs SCE

Electroplating solution composition			(-) Deposition current (mA cm ⁻²)		Film thickness (10 ⁻⁵ cm)	Photopotential (mV)	Corrosion rate (mpy)
Zn	Se	Co	Initial	Final			
0.1	0.01	0.0000	0.850	0.050	4.8	160	1.6
0.1	0.01	0.0001	0.930	0.090	5.6	180	1.0
0.1	0.01	0.0002	1.040	0.110	6.0	190	0.8
0.1	0.01	0.0003	1.080	0.130	6.8	190	0.5
0.1	0.01	0.0004	1.100	0.150	7.7	175	0.5

shown in Fig 2. The charging current is markedly affected by electrode materials and this can be explained in terms of charge injection. The primary source of charge carriers is the electrode contact, a potential difference is created between the two surfaces. The semiconducting surface differs

from a metal surface. However, in that an electric field may exist within the interior of the semiconductor. For this reason the contact potential drop between the metal and semiconductor may take place within the material rather than at the contact surfaces. Along with the field, there may exist a depletion in the accumulation of charges in the surface layers. The work function of the semiconducting material is higher compared to that of the metal used for contacts, which creates an accumulation layer at the interfaces and leaves charge carriers in the bulk. Release of a large number of charge carriers from the electrode surface during deposition may then lead to blocking of electrode surface. This may also be one of the reason for decreasing in current during potentiostatic deposition. The film thickness (F_c) values have been calculated⁹.

The film thickness values for Ni and Co containing ZnSe are included in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. This shows that the film thickness values increases with the successive addition of nickel and cobalt incorporation during deposition. These electrodeposited films were tested for their photoactivity¹⁰. The results are presented in the Tables 1 and 2. The photopotentials data show that there is a marked improvement in photoactivity due to increased inclusion of nickel and cobalt in the electroplating solution. Photoaction spectral studies reveal that the threshold wavelength changes

Fig. 2. Variation of current density with time during deposition of (◆) ZnSe, (■) 0.0002 M Ni containing ZnSe and (Δ) 0.0002 M Co containing ZnSe.

Fig. 3. Photoaction spectra of (u) ZnSe, (n) 0.0002 M Ni and (D) 0.0002 M Co containing ZnSe thin films.

perceptibly with composition. It is shifted towards higher wavelength with increase in nickel and cobalt concentration. These results indicate that the increased inclusion of nickel and cobalt in the electrodeposits result in lowering of its band gap. The typical plots are shown in Fig. 3 for ZnSe, Ni and Co containing ZnSe films.

When a metal electrode is in equilibrium with the electrolyte, the anodic current and cathodic currents are equal and no net reaction occurs. If this equilibrium is altered by an external bias, the metal surface becomes polarised. Polarisation is associated with two processes. A net flow of current and a net shift of the electrode potential from equilibrium. These phenomena are the basis of the electrochemical corrosion. To construct Tafel plots for the estimation of corrosion behaviour of ZnSe, Ni and Co containing ZnSe films, variation of current with potential was studied (Fig. 4)^{11,12}.

Fig. 4. The Tafel plots of (u) ZnSe, (n) 0.0002 M Ni and (D) 0.0002 M Co containing ZnSe thin films.

Corrosion rates of different electrodeposites of Ni and Co containing ZnSe are included in the Tables 1 and 2. It has been seen that the corrosion rates decreases as the nickel and cobalt concentration increases. This reveals that the electrodeposites containing Ni as well as Co are less corrosive.

On the basis of the result presented above, it may be inferred that the preparation of nickel and cobalt containing ZnSe polycrystalline thin films are photoactive and with improved corrosion resistant.

Experimental

With the help of electrochemical co-deposition method (using three electrode setup), zinc selenide, nickel and cobalt containing zinc selenide thin film were prepared^{13,14}. Platinum plates (1 cm× 1 cm) were cleaned with emery paper and washed with acetone and deionised water respectively. When it got dried, a thick copper wire was attached on one of its side using silver epoxy for ohmic contact. The back side and edges of each of the platinum plates were covered with an insulating araldite cement. One platinum electrode was used as working electrode, another as a counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as a reference electrode.

These electrodes were kept in the electroplating solution containing ZnSO₄ (A.R.), SeO₂ (Fluka), NiSO₄ (C.D.H.) and CoSO₄ having desired composition. The potential of the working electrode was maintained to an optimal value with respect to SCE using a platinum counter electrode with the help of power supply (Systronics). Then corresponding current was measured with the help of a digital multimeter (Systronics). The electrodeposited thin films were tested for their photoelectroactivity using an illumination chamber having 1000 W lamp. The photopotential was measured along with digital multimeter with an accuracy of 0.1 mV. Photoaction data were obtained with the help of a monochromator (Applied Photophysics, London). In order to obtain Tafel plots, current-voltage behaviour was examined for the purpose of investigation of corrosion characteristics of electrodeposited thin films.

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